

A Proposed Energy Management System (EMS) for a Residential Microgrid

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Abstract: *Abstract— This paper proposes an energy management system (EMS) of a microgrid comprised of a solar photovoltaic array, wind turbine, and a battery energy storage system, for a residential building positioned in a remote area. The aim is to design a control system that will equitably manage generated energy to meet the load demand. The power generated by the microgrid is modelled to supply the residential load and charge the battery simultaneously. The battery storage will only be dispatched as the last resource to meet the load demand deficit when the combined power generated from the microgrid is unable to sustain the residential load demand. Modelling and simulation are performed using Matlab/Simulink.*

Keywords:

Photovoltaic system, Wind system, Battery storage system, micro-grid, Residential household, energy management.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The implementation of a microgrid based on renewable energy systems is a big aid in terms of fighting the energy crisis, and the pollution of the atmosphere due to the high population growth [1]. The implementation either on a large or small scale microgrid has been promoted around the world in order to increase access to electricity in rural areas where there is no network and in urban areas. However, these intermittent renewable energy resources are not able to operate continuously, for example, solar irradiation is only available during the day, while wind speed changes from time to time [2]. Therefore, for a reliable operation of the microgrid, storage systems are needed [2]. The South African government has set a plan to integrate renewable energy systems into the national grid as a response to the increased energy demand. The energy generated via renewable energy systems is supposed to reach 17.8 GW by the year 2030, and will be 20% of all generated power in South-Africa [3].

In recent years, many researchers have studied the energy management of a microgrid. Authors in [4] presented the model that enables the integration of a microgrid renewable energy into a grid, by proposing a web-based platform for dynamic demand response. In [5], and [6], the authors proposed a method that integrates PV, wind, and a battery system for a smart home. Authors in [7] studied the integration of smart interconnection

control for a hybrid microgrid system composed of a wind turbine, and a photovoltaic system connected to the grid. A reactive power control system was also investigated. Authors in [8] studied the mismatch between generation and consumption time, and adopted a sharing method to reduce transmission losses. Authors in [9] addressed the energy management issue for a smart home integrated with photovoltaic and battery storage systems. The optimization of energy flow between energy generated and consumption devices, by taking into account peak and off-peak time, was controlled by a two-way communication protocol. Authors in [10] considered a daily variation of the load for both summer and winter periods, and used quadratic programming to simulate the model. Authors in [11] presented the application of the tracking system to capture the maximum possible wind speed and solar radiation, by orienting wind turbine blade and photovoltaic panel system in the right direction of solar irradiation and wind. In [12], authors investigated the operating strategies which can increase the cycle of the battery, by applying intelligent operating strategies, such as PV-BESS, without changing load consumption. Authors in [13] considered minimization of the system cost, by reducing energy consumption and emission of CO₂, where certain rules relating to the operating of diesel generator have been applied. Authors in [14] proposed the integration of three different batteries such as vanadium redox flow, lead-acid, and lithium-ion, in order to enhance the efficiency of

the system. Authors in [15], proposed the integration of distributed storage to improve the hosting ability between load and distributed generation. Day-ahead operation strategy and optimal capacity with the cost of the distribution system, and the cost of battery cycling was taken as two primary factors. Authors in [16] developed a multifunctional energy storage system to reduce the use of fossil fuel energy, where the structural electric double-layer capacitors (EDLC) and structural dielectric capacitors were introduced. Authors in [17] applied the integration of supercapacitor energy storage for a grid-connected system in order to store energy, and to reduce load fluctuations in response to lightning fault currents, and non-uniform load distribution.

Therefore, there are still many problems regarding the implementation of energy management of a microgrid that need to be addressed such as: how distributed energy resources can be integrated and managed to sustain a residential household located in rural areas; how good management of distributed energy resources can help the rural area and; which combination of distributed energy resources is suitable for these areas. In this paper, a proposed energy management system (EnMS) is presented for a residential microgrid. The microgrid model will use a storage battery as a backup system to store energy from the intermittent sources (PV and wind), then in a case where energy from renewable energy systems is not enough to sustain the load, power will be drawn from the battery. Matlab will be used to simulate and test the performance of the energy management system of a microgrid.

II. BLOCK DIAGRAM OF PROPOSED MICROGRID

Microgrid is a small generation power system which can be operated either independently or combined with other small generation power grids. However, as illustrated in the flow chart diagram in Fig 1. There is a wind turbine, a photovoltaic panel (PV), battery, and load. The loads are divided into three groups; AC load, low consumption DC load (light, and mobile phone, etc) and a Dump load. The way the system works is that first of all power from microgrid renewable energy (wind and PV) will be used to supply both AC and DC load at the same time. In case power from renewable energy become more than the load the excess power should be used to charge the battery, and in case the state of charge (SOC) of a battery is at the maximum the excess power will be dumped. Hence, in an event that the power produced by the microgrid is less than the base load, the battery should supply adequate power to meet the load. This happens especially during the night when there is a lack of solar irradiance. Overall sizing of

a proposed system comprised of PV, wind turbine, and battery system was done using homer software and modified in order to avoid the wastage of energy and the cost related to the system

Fig. 1. Block diagram of a microgrid renewable system comprised with solar PV-wind, and battery hybrid system.

III. MATHEMATICAL MODELING OF THE MICROGRID

A. Photovoltaic System Model

The PV model used in this research is a Soltech PV model and is a fixed model. Therefore, the maximum power point tracking system known as MPPT was used with the P&O algorithm to extract the maximum possible power from PV. Therefore, power produced by the PV array is expressed by [10]:

$$P_{pv} = \eta_{pv} A_c I_{pv}$$

Where η_{pv} is the efficiency of PV arrays, A_c is the area where PV is mounted, I_{pv} is the solar irradiation which reached to the solar panels at NT, NT is the nominal and standard cell operating temperature condition. ($1 \text{ kWh/m}^2/\text{day}$), P_{pv} is the output power generated by the PV arrays. With [10]:

$$\eta_{pv} = \eta_R \left[1 - 0.9\beta \left(\frac{I_{pv}}{I_{pv,NT}} \right) (T_{c,NT} - T_{a,NT}) - \beta(T_a - T_R) \right] \quad (2)$$

Where η_R is the reference temperature efficiency, T_a is the ambient temperature, T_R is the reference temperature, $T_{c,NT}$ is the temperature of a cell, and β is temperature coefficient, and $I_{pv,NT}$ is the average solar irradiation falling on the surface of a PV, at NT [10]. Table I, presents different input parameters of a Fresnel photovoltaic system. Simulation was conducted using Sim Power System (SPS) toolbox from Matlab/Simulink.

Table I: Photovoltaic input parameter

Photovoltaic Model	input	Unit
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parameter	
Module	1Soltech 1STH-230-P
Maximum Power (W)	228.735
Open Circuit Voltage Voc (V)	37.1
Voltage at Maximum power point V_{mp} (V)	29.9
Short-circuit current I_{SC} (A)	8.18
Current at maximum power point Imp (A)	7.65
Temperature coefficient of Voc (%/deg.C)	0.102
Cells per module (N_{Cell})	60

B. Wind system model

The wind model used in this study is a permanent magnet synchronous generator (PMSG) with 230V, 5kW, and 50Hz as frequency. Therefore, the equation (3) expressed wind turbine power [18]:

$$P_w = \frac{1}{2} \eta_{wt} C_p(\lambda, \beta) \rho A v^3 \quad (3)$$

V is the velocity of the wind hitting the turbine blades, A is the area swept by wind turbine rotor (m^2), C_p is the efficiency of the rotor, and ρ is the air density at the height of the turbine hub, and η_{wt} is the turbine efficiency, β is the pitch angle of the blade, and λ is the rotor blade tip speed ratio to wind speed [8]. In case, we have an average wind speed V_{avg} , the average power in the wind is just [19]:

$$P_{wt} = \frac{6}{\pi} \cdot \frac{1}{2} \eta_{wt} \rho_{air} C_p A v_{avg}^3 \quad (4)$$

The following equation is used by adjusting the wind speed to the height of the turbine hub [19]:

$$v_{hub} = v_{ref} \left(\frac{H_{hub}}{H_{ref}} \right)^\beta \quad (5)$$

β is used to reflect the effects of the land and how it interacts with the wind. v_{ref} , v_{hub} are respectively the speed of wind at the reference and at the hub. H_{hub} , H_{ref} are the hub and reference speed measured height respectively [19].

Table II: Wind input parameter

Wind Turbine Parameters	Unit
Mechanical Power output (kW)	5
Cut-in Speed (m/s)	1.5
Base Wind Speed (m/s)	12
Cut-out Speed (m/s)	14
Pitch angle	0
Base rotational speed (pu)	1

C. Battery bank model

The chosen battery is a Lithium-Ion battery. Two-row of 19 Lithium-Ion batteries are connected in series each one with 12V and 20Ah which gives a total of 228V and 20Ah, and an overall 9120 Wh. Therefore, the state of charge (SOC) for the battery at time (t) is expressed by the initial state of charge, which depend on the charging and discharging of power [20]:

$$SOC(t + \Delta t) = SOC(t) + \eta_{batt} \left(\frac{P_B(t)}{V_{bus}} \right) \Delta t \quad (6)$$

$SOC(t)$ is the state of charge, $SOC(t + \Delta t)$ is a battery discharging and charging amount, η_{batt} is a battery efficiency, $P_B(t)$ is battery power, Δt is step time and V_{bus} is bus voltage. Therefore, the minimum discharge limit is expressed by (7) [20]:

$$SOC_{min} = (1 - DOD) SOC_{max} \quad (7)$$

Where, DOD is the depth of discharge.

Table III: Input parameter of Battery

Battery Model Input Parameters	Unit
Rated battery voltage (V)	12
Battery Capacity (Ah)	20
Maximum Capacity of a battery (Ah)	20
Fully Charged Voltage (V)	12
Nominal Discharge Current (A)	6.521
State of charge of battery (%)	69
Battery Voltage Response time (sec)	0.1

D. DC/DC Boost Converter System

A boost unidirectional converter model connected to the photovoltaic which raised the dc voltage of 120V from the photovoltaic system to 230V DC bus. The converter is comprised of inductor L , capacitor C , Diodes D , load resistance, and main switch S . however, boost converter is controlled by P&O.

Table IV: Input parameter of the DC/DC boost converter

Inverter Parameters	Model	Input	Unit
Input Voltage (Vin)			120
Output Voltage (Vout)			230
Converter efficiency			0.9
Switching Frequency			15000 Hz
Inductance (L)			0987789 e-3
Capacitance (C)			37353e-4
Resistance (R)			15.343

E. AC/DC Inverter

AC-DC rectifier is used to change AC voltage from wind turbines to DC voltage to be able to introduce wind model in the system.

F. DC/AC Rectifier

The DC to AC converter is connected to change DC voltage from renewable energy to AC voltage to be able to supply the AC load located in the residential house. Therefore, 230 DC voltage is converted to 230 AC voltage

IV. ENERGY MAGEMENT SYSTEM (EMS)

The proposed energy management system has been applied in this study in order to give accurate energy sharing of the microgrid system due to the uncertainty of renewable energy sources which in turn leads to the mismatch between load and the supply. However, there are many types of energy management systems that can be used to guarantee the equitable sharing of energy between different sources. Therefore, the state machine control system has been chosen to monitor, control, and share energy due to its efficiency, and robustness. Therefore, some condition has been implemented to fully control the flow of energy between intermittent sources and load.

First of all, renewable energy generated by photovoltaic (PV) and wind turbine is used to supply the load demand of a residential building. In case the power generated from renewable sources exceed the residential load demand, the excess is used to charge the battery. If the battery state of charge becomes more than 90% the battery will automatically have to disconnect. Note that the battery will be used as a back-up. However, in case renewable power generated is more than load demand and state of charge of a battery is at the highest level the dump load will be connected in order to avoid the frequency disturbance and any other damage. Hence, dump load will only on in case the battery state of charge is at the highest level, and while the power from renewable is higher than load demand.

In case renewable power becomes less than residential load power, the algorithm will check the state of charge of a battery. In case the state of charge of the battery will be at its normal charge level condition or high charged level, the battery will automatically connect to the load to supply the unsatisfied or unmet load. However, in order to boost the performance of a battery, the algorithm will be able to check the state of charge of the

battery and impose the rule for the operation of the battery, in case the state of charge of a battery is less than its lower level, the battery is disconnected to prevent damage. Hence, all the loads demand is disconnected.

- *Condition of state machine control system*

- *If $P_{ren} \geq P_{Load}$ && $SOC < 40\%$*

Charging = 1; Discharging= 0; Load1On= 1; Load2On= 1; $D_{Load}=0$;

The power from renewable (PV and Wind) in this case will be used to supply the load and the excess will be used to charge the battery. In case the state of charge (SOC) of a battery gets to the maximum the braking resistor will operate so that the life cycle of a battery system will be boosted.

- *If $P_{ren} \geq P_{Load}$ && $SOC > 40\%$:&& $SOC < 90\%$*

Charging = 1; Discharging= 0; Load1On= 1; Load2On= 1; $D_{Load} = 0$;

In this case, as the battery state is at the normal state where it can be able to charge or discharge at any time, the excess power from renewable energy will be used to charge a battery. Dump load will not be necessary to be connected due to the fact that the power will be used for both supplying the load and charging the battery in case there is excess power.

- *If $P_{ren} \geq P_{Load}$ && $SOC > 90\%$*

Charing = 0; Discharging= 0; Load1On= 1; Load2On= 1; $D_{Load}=1$;

In this case as the SOC of a battery is at its highest level of charging, the excess power from renewable energy will connect to the Dump load in order to avoid overpowering.

- *If else $P_{ren} < P_{Load}$ && $40 < SOC < 90\%$*

Charging=0; Discharging= 1; Load1On=1; Load2On= 1; $D_{Load}=0$;

In case the renewable energy is not able to sustain the load demand, the algorithm will check the battery state of charge. In case the battery SOC is at its normal level, the power will be drawn from a battery to supply the unsatisfied load. Both loads will be connected but the dump load will not be connected.

- *If else $P_{ren} < P_{Load}$ && $SOC > 90\%$*

Charging=0; Discharging= 1; Load1On=1;
Load2On= 1; D_{Load}=0;

In case, renewable energy is not enough to sustain the load, the algorithm will check the SOC of a battery, in case the SOC of a battery is at the highest level, the unsatisfied load will be compensated by a battery.

- If else $P_{ren} < P_{Load}$ && $SOC < 40\%$

First condition

$P_{ren} \geq P_{L1}$
Charge = 1; Discharge =0; Load1On=1;
Load2On= 0; D_{Load}=0;

Second Condition

$P_{ren} \geq P_{L2}$
Charge = 1; Discharge =0; Load1On=0;
Load2On= 1; D_{Load}=0;

Otherwise

Charge = 1; Discharge =0; Load1On=0;
Load2On= 0; D_{Load}=0;

In case the power from renewable energy is not able to supply the load, and the SOC of battery is less than its minimum, the algorithm will check the available power from renewable sources and compare to the load one in case renewable power is equal or higher than load one, the algorithm will disconnect load two, in case renewable power is less than load one, the algorithm will check load two, if found that renewable power is higher or equal than load two, load one will be disconnected and connect both load two and battery, if-else renewable power is less than load two, both loads should be disconnected.

V. CASE STUDY

A. Load Profile of a Residential House

The study was carried out on a residential household located in Cape Town/ South Africa, with latitude, and longitude of 33° 55,5'S, 18° 25,4'E, and elevation of 25 m. However, energy consumption is presented for all appliances in the first row of Fig. 4. Therefore, the load demand is classified into three categories, the first is considered as the main load which in turn split into three sub load which are not on at the same time but each one is considered to be on at different times as seen in 1st, 2nd and 3rd row of Fig. 3. The second one is a secondary load comprised with two sub loads connected at different times as seen in the 3rd and 4th row of Fig. 3, then the third load is a Dump load which can be connected only

in case the energy generated by renewable sources is higher than the load demand and the state of a battery is at the maximum level.

Fig 2. Energy sharing algorithm

Fig 3. Switches of Load Demand

VI. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The energy management system was implemented using state machine in order to execute the load sharing between different renewable energy sources such as photovoltaic, wind turbine and battery system. The 5000 W wind turbine with 230V was connected with a PV of 4000 W with 120V connected to a dc/dc boost converter driven by MPPT and change it to 230 dc voltage. However, the battery model was set to be at 230V and the initial state of charge is 69%. However, according to Fig. 4, the first row presents the power consumed by the residential building (Load Power) With peak demands occurred at the 20s to 30s with almost 11000 W, while the next row shows the SOC of a battery, The charging and discharging is conducted as seen on the second row, it is seen that the battery starts charging at the beginning till the

5th second, and due to the rising of load, from 10th second to 20th second the battery state of charge decreases a little bit, from 20th second to the 30th second SOC decreased, then from 30th second to 50th second the SOC is increasing due to the rise of renewable energy and also the decreasing of the load. The third row shows the energy generated by a wind turbine which in terms reach a peak of 5000 W, the next row is the power generated by photovoltaic which goes between 3000 W and 4000 W.

Fig. 4, Power Load, Power Generated by Renewable Energy and Operational State of battery

VII. CONCLUSIONS

This study has basically focused on the integration of energy management of the microgrid system comprised with a photovoltaic system (PV), Wind turbine, and battery energy storage system for a residential house. However, energy management and energy flow between intermittent sources have been presented in this study using a sim power toolbox from Simulink/Matlab. Therefore, results show that the proposed model has the potential under various operation models to share energy generated despite the uncertainty of renewable sources. However, the drawback of the proposed model is that the surplus power generated from renewable energy can only be sent to the dump load to avoid excess generated energy or increase

the number of battery storage in order to be able to store all generated power which in turn will increase the prices of the system. Therefore, we recommend that the next research will introduce a grid to the system in order to be able to sell the surplus energy to the grid to get extra money.

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